

DEFENSE ATM NETWORK SERVICES AND DESIGN

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Abstract - This paper presents intelligent network services and performance analysis methods for planning, designing, operating, and managing the evolving defense Asynchronous Transfer Mode (ATM) network. The Defense Information Systems Network (DISN) uses ATM high-speed networks and IP services to support multiple types of traffic classes with high performance. The DISN will deploy ATM architecture and emulated LAN services to accommodate a wide variety of traffic types. This paper focuses on IP-over-ATM services that are key to the future DISN and addresses technical issues concerning the quality-of-service (QoS). Traffic characterization and analysis of ATM networks, capacity management and sizing, and allocation of network resources in response to new requirements are studied. The performance analysis, monitoring, and operational effectiveness are then examined. The intelligent network design and analysis methods using modeling and simulation tools to support the complete life cycle of the DISN ATM are also described.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Defense Information Systems Agency (DISA) supports a full spectrum of communications services for peacetime and warfighting activities. It is currently operating and developing the DISN with ATM services to provide integrated, wideband, wide-area networking capabilities. The DISN with emerging ATM technology will provide not only responsive communications services but also multiple types of information services such as voice, data, video, and point-to-point bandwidth services. This paper presents intelligent network services and operations of the current and planned DISN ATM networks with focus on the performance evaluation of the involved networks. Since the DISN is so vast in dimension and serves multiple types of traffic, innovative analytical and simulation techniques must be employed. In designing and implementing new DISN services, traffic characterization of all applications, end-to-end performance, capacity sizing/planning, and proper allocation of resources are key elements. Establishment of methodologies for inserting the modern network technology, obtaining feedback for further development, and accelerating transfer of the new technology are immediate concerns for the DISN ATM.

The main goal of this paper is to study the ATM architecture with intelligent services, systems engineering, and network management concepts for DISN. By supporting the ATM-based network in the area of C4I, the overall information services to the warrior will be provided in a timely and cost effective manner. The DISN is the major communications service component for the evolving Defense Information

Infrastructure (DII) with integrated information services. One of the primary advantages of ATM bring to DII is its capability to support true voice, data, and video traffic integration with guaranteed QoS for all traffic types. The schematic view of the DoD ATM communications architecture using the Broadband Integrated Services Digital Network (B-ISDN) and its network implementations is given by Figure 1.

To develop, implement, operate, and maintain the DISN, various modeling techniques are currently used for capacity planning, performance analysis, monitoring, and evaluating the behavior of the managed network. The high capacity communications networks span the world with modern multiplexers, power hubs, and ATM switches to meet and serve the growing demands. Moreover, there have been new ATM-based services and emergence of a new class of image-intensive interactive applications. The DISN ATM network will also interact with special purpose networks for leading-edge services, high speed computing, communication research environment, multimedia conferencing, distributed simulation, and training, as part of a global grid to government and commercial networks. Since ATM network enables communications services for users, virtual connections and their management become more critical. Information assurance is also becoming a key issue.

ATM is a technology for consolidating voice, data, and video traffic over high-speed, cell-based links and has gained widespread support in both industry and the military over the past few years. The main benefit of ATM is that it provides a common switching and transmission architecture for many traffic types. The DoD has installed ATM systems and components on a limited basis and is beginning to make widespread use of the technology with emulated LAN services. The ATM/SONET applications relate to near-term and far-term DISN. The global grid concept through the use of advanced ATM/SONET technologies will provide a seamless end-to-end

Figure 1. Communications Architecture of DISN ATM.

information exchange environment. This paper will next discuss the development of systems engineering mechanisms and network management plans for the DISN ATM services to provide better operational support to all users. The modeling tools have been used for capacity planning (sizing), performance analysis, monitoring, and evaluating the network behavior.

The DISN ATM is currently employed as a transport for much of DoD's IP services. To this end, edge devices such as power hubs are connected to ATM switches to provide LAN emulation (LANE) services. In addition, multiprotocol over ATM (MPOA) services are envisioned for the near-term DISN. This paper addresses modeling and technology concerns for the evolution of DISN ATM networks.

Of all aspects of ATM networks, this paper focuses on modeling and performance assessment aspects of implementing new DISN ATM services. For multiple types of ATM services, appropriate network design and performance evaluation methodologies will be provided. Innovative analytical techniques are combined with simulation capabilities to evaluate performance of the networks and the level of quality of service.

II. DISN ATM NETWORK SERVICES

Currently, IP traffic is widely in operation within DISN and it interoperates with ATM-based communication entities. To implement the ATM technology for high-speed multimedia services, the objective ATM networks are being deployed and expanded. While voice service still plays a role in driving future network directions, emerging multi-media applications will incorporate both voice and data. For the new DISN services, both centralized and distributed control concepts through ATM networking will be employed for the network operation and management. By doing so, multimedia on-demand services will be effectively provided with high performance and guaranteed QoS. Automated collection and estimation of existing and planned traffic requirements constitute an essential part for designing and managing the evolving DISN.

ATM will provide solid benefits to the entire spectrum of DoD users. It will provide bandwidth efficiency with capability to handle bursty traffic. ATM not only offers the capability to support the time-sensitive traffic such as voice and video, but it also offers enhanced delivery options such as multicasting and broadcasting. ATM is scalable in that many users, such as LANs, switches, and public networks can use the same cell format since different systems with the same message format can adjust rates.

ATM possesses network granularity in that it allows the network to be tailored to the application, rather than forcing applications to the network. ATM allows the user to deliver traffic at rates and degrees of burstyness compatible with the applications running. In contrast to frame relay, ATM's short, fixed, cell size points the way to high-speed self routing switching. ATM provides network flexibility as a vehicle for virtual private networks, bringing the same advantages of carrier-based virtual private networks. ATM will bring about lower operation and management costs than conventional networking due to high performance and speed. SONET operations, administration, maintenance, and provisioned features can also be cooperatively used.

The main disadvantage of using ATM technology is however its time required to deploy and make it available to all users. The lack of applications development has discouraged early adoption of ATM. Operational costs remain high at the present time, and the cost of managing the network may exceed the hardware and software costs. Outstanding issues such as security, congestion control, network management, and standardization have to be fully resolved for all requirements. Even high-performance ATM-based networks will sometimes experience failures, network congestion, and periods of degraded performance. Thus, without proper and intelligent network management practices, the vitality of the large-scale ATM network may be compromised.

For DISN, SONET is used to work both with the synchronous transfer mode used by circuit switches and ATM. ATM and SONET will provide services and characteristics that fulfill the general requirements of DoD communications. Such services include commonality of backbone technology, high-speed transmissions, fixed cell size providing protection against loss of information, international standards, interoperability, assured network access during periods of congestion, and minimal human intervention during connection setup.

Through the virtual path capabilities of ATM, flexible bandwidth provisioning, network path restoration, and intelligent network control and management are realized. Dynamic rerouting in case of link/node failures, and intelligent network diagnostics, and decoupling of path/bandwidth will be effectively implemented. ATM has also proven to have low latency characteristics and is presumably be better than the existing wideband TDM switching technology.

The other challenges for ATM networking exist in the areas of emulated LAN (ELAN) services centered on power hubs. Services in multiplexing, network control and management, SONET interface design, fast Ethernet interfaces with premises networks, tactical or deployed, must be provided seamlessly To avoid potential negative impact when a substantial number of ATM switches are abruptly added to the DISN, a deliberate, objective ATM backbone is being implemented. The architectural layout of the evolving DoD ATM network is illustrated by Figure 2.

To resolve address conflicts while servicing IP-over-ATM traffic, ATM Address Resolution Protocol (ARP) servers are

Figure 2. ATM Virtual Path Network with ELAN Services.

deployed. To further support ATM ELAN services, including broadcasting services, the LAN emulation client (LEC) server, LAN emulation server (LES), and Broadcast and Unknown Server (BUS) are specified for ELANs. To interconnect all of these networks, all ATM components and interfaces have to be deployed as tailored for DoD standards and requirements. The new deployed systems will perform address resolution and buffering to process IP and ATM traffic demands through physical and virtual routing, cell buffering, and native ATM switching.

Key elements to be considered in operating the ATM DISN are high-speed switching, optical switching, protocol transparent networking, control algorithms, interoperability, reliability, availability, and global grid. All ATM communications elements will work together to operate the DISN cost effectively with high performance and conform to modern communications standards and requirements.

III. DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF ATM NETWORKS

This section presents the methods to analyze the performance of large-scale ATM network architectures with multiple types of communications services. ATM networks provide a wide range of fixed and variable rate services in an integrated manner. For high-speed ATM networks, new types of virtual path (VP) routing mechanisms are used to transfer a large amount of data traffic volumes seamlessly. Data traffic is assigned to different classes depending on its priority and origin-destination pair. SONET overhead, ATM adaptation, cell processing, flexible virtual path routing, and network restoration are special features of ATM services. The DISN ATM network will use hierarchical routing to serve multiple types of traffic traversing the wideband transmission media and high-speed switches, hubs, and routers.

To implement ATM network services in the future DISN, User-Network Interface (UNI) and Network-Network Interface (NNI) of OC3 or higher rates will be used to serve multiple types of traffic. ATM/SONET network layers are the foundation of protocols to interconnect various networks. Through ATM-based protocols, flow control, error handling, message segmentation, and handling of continuous/bursty traffic are effectively done.

In the new high-speed network environment with fiber media and ATM switches, queueing delays may be almost negligible but the time required to set up a connection path must be still accounted for. Cells requesting a direct path must wait in buffer at an initiating node until a path is available to them. Aided with high-speed transmission media, virtual path routing are attainable for most end users. It has been widely known that, as the message length gets larger, the virtual path routing begins to show better performance. Thus, ATM technology will bring forth high performance for the DISN services in handling modern high volume traffic with lengthy messages.

For ATM, two hierarchical levels are defined; virtual channel and virtual path. These two identifiers allow virtual connections to take place. Virtual Path Connection (VPC) and Virtual Channel Connection (VCC) are efficiently handled through intelligent ATM management. For smaller messages, VPC/VCC may not require much management. But for larger

messages, VPC/VCC would become more essential since permanent virtual connections are suitable for detailed management. The virtual connection is established and disestablished via a special mechanism of using bit streams containing no data.

To support the ATM/SONET technology, DoD has embarked on building its own ATM backbone network for meeting all information demands relying less on carrier ATM clouds (see [3]). The planned objective ATM backbone network is illustrated by Figure 3. The network will interconnect end user computers, routers, Web stations, power hubs, and regional ATM switches. The network with up to OC12 rate links proves significant economies of scale not only for consolidating all heterogeneous networks, but also for supporting the high data traffic volume expected of the ever growing ATM applications.

ATM switches perform automatic routing via alternate virtual paths. As an immediate extension of the traditional dynamic adaptive routing, modern high-capacity switches and transmission media will use specific routing mechanisms for fractionized channels of broadband links. The ATM cell-relay interfaces are designed to route cell packets using a path at high speed with minimum path delays. This new routing falls into a class of virtual circuit switching. However, cell packets in the network may have to undergo several routing algorithms on their way to their final destinations. All data sent between endpoints will be transmitted on a fixed path or virtual path for the entire duration of a session.

Figure 3. DISN SONET Backbone Network.

ATM networks will have the capabilities of flexible bandwidth provisioning, fast network restoration, and high intelligent networking. To perform these functions, dynamic rerouting, operation diagnostics, decoupling of paths, inband signaling, and priority control cell transport must be done effectively. From new ATM networking, DoD end users will experience reduced deployment risks with one consolidated network, lower costs with economies of scale, simplified network operation and management, flexible bandwidth capabilities, and standardized interfaces.

Major ATM services supported by different AALs (ATM Adaptation Layers) are: constant bit rate (CBR) service (type 1) with end-to-end timing, connection oriented; Variable bit rate (VBR) real time (RT) service (type 2) with end-to-end timing, connection oriented; Connection-oriented VBR with non-real time (NRT) (type 3); Available bit rate (ABR) (type 4),

connectionless data transfer with no timing; and Unspecified bit rate (UBR) (type 5) such as Simple and Efficient Adaptation Layer (SEAL) services.

Various systems engineering elements of the current and future DISN ATM network operations need to be considered. Some principles and characteristics of ATM networks are discussed next.

a. Network, Systems, and Users Requirements: The current and future traffic demands and user requirements can be collected and estimated in an efficient manner by setting up automated mechanisms. Whenever an uncertainty arises, scientific modeling and analysis will be used. Intelligent directory services can also be set up for this purpose.

b. Multimedia Broadband Operations: SMDS, FRS, and ATM/SONET all provide multimedia services for voice, data, video, and imagery. Traffic requirements for each type can be either time continuum of a media stream or synchronization between media streams. These operations will require exchanges of operations information between various nodes in the network to coordinate the multiple traffic operations and management.

c. Dynamic Resource Allocation: The resources (nodes, links, computer, routers, gateways, etc.) allocated to a type of traffic can be static at the time of connection setup or dynamic during a message session. Static or dynamic resource allocation has implications with respect to connection control/autonomy, communications link routing, and bandwidth allocation. ATM protocols support all these properties.

d. Message Length: Messages are concatenated or fragmented while being processed by the network. Concatenation is necessary to utilize a wide bandwidth and to execute certain communications protocols. Fragmentation is done to partition messages into smaller ones to implement routing algorithms. Since ATM uses cells to transport information, message fragmentation is important.

e. Dynamic Hierarchical Routing: The dynamic routing uses metrics to find the optimum path given each source-destination pair. For connectionless traffic, the routing can be done in a classical sense. In this case, the routing metric for type m traffic along a path from node i to node j , is recursively computed by

$$D_n^m(i, j) = \min_{k \in N(i)} [d_{n-1}^m(i, k) + D_{n-1}^m(k, j)] \quad (1)$$

where $d_{n-1}^m(i, k)$ is the routing metric for link (i, k) at time $n-1$. The routing metric takes into account such factors as delays, link costs, balanced utilization, and addressing.

For connection-oriented, different switched virtual path routing algorithms can be used. The optimum path for packets or cells originating from i and destined for j is determined by solving

$$D_n^m(i, j) = \min_{p \in P_{ij}} [D_n^m(i, j | p)] \quad (2)$$

where P_{ij} is the set of all alternate paths from node i to node j . Each packet or cell will follow nodes along the selected p^* . The routing metrics can have any arbitrary forms, as a nonlinear function of delays, distances, utilization, and link capacities.

f. Traffic, Congestion, and Flow Control: ATM networks reserve bandwidth for connection-oriented services and enforce limits on access to the services. ATM peak cell rate (PCR) and sustainable cell rate (SCR) traffic control functions are provided on the virtual connection basis. ATM leaky bucket configurations are used for such purposes.

Congestion control complements the routing algorithm to produce high performance. Throttling can be locally implemented to alleviate network congestion whenever appropriate. Network characteristics involved in congestion control are queueing strategy, service scheduling, discard strategy, route selections, propagation delay, processing delay, and connection mode. Application characteristics impacted by congestion control are connection mode, retransmission policy, acknowledgement policy, responsiveness, and flow control.

ATM networks implement flow control that can be window-based, rate-based, or credit based. Data flows may detect and react to congestion on either by a link-by-link basis, or by an end-to-end basis. ATM routing capabilities will further automate the flow control process to reduce retransmission. ATM's high processing power allows more advanced flow control and windowing mechanisms at end systems, lessening the burden on the network side.

g. Dynamic Bandwidth Capacity Assignment: The link capacity to assign can also be determined analytically. Excess bandwidth may be used for other applications. Let λ_i be the measured traffic flow at link i and let T_{\max} be the maximum allowable network delay. Also let C_i be the maximum capacity for link i and let $1/\mu$ denote the average message length. Given the updated traffic flows at a given time, the optimal capacity of the link is determined as (see Jo and Sykes [4])

$$C_i^* = \min[\lambda_i / \mu + \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_i(w_2 - \psi)}{\Gamma \mu w_1 d_i}}, C_i] \quad (3)$$

where w_1 and w_2 are weight constants for transmission time and delay, respectively. ψ is the nonnegative Lagrangian multiplier that will be computed during the optimization process.

h. Reliability and Availability: The reliability of an ATM network can be maintained by rerouting and intelligent system diagnostics. In case of a network failure, network restoration must be done expeditiously. The grade of service can be measured in terms of the virtual path reliability. There are in total R_{ij} number of virtual paths available from node i to node j . For the r th virtual path there are $M_{ij}(r)$ links in series. Let p_s denote link availability for link s . Then the reliability of the virtual path (i, j) is computed by

$$p(i, j) = \prod_{r=1}^{R_{ij}} (1 - \prod_{s=1}^{M_{ij}(r)} p_s) \quad (4)$$

This virtual path reliability/availability information will be effectively used for related performance attributes.

IV. ATM ARCHITECTURE PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The DISN ATM laydown architecture is next presented and the associated network performance evaluation methodologies are discussed. IP-over-ATM services are immediate network provisioning for DISN ATM services. To implement such services, high-capacity power hubs are deployed to constitute national or regional ELANs. Routers will be connected to ATM switches via power hubs and then constitute logical IP subnets. Traffic analysis and performance analysis are immediate tasks for IP-over-ATM services. Intelligent network management concepts are used to enhance the performance level, and innovative modeling and simulation are used for the future ATM objective network design.

The near-term DISN ATM architecture will provide ELAN services through edge devices around ATM backbone. How to serve IP traffic over the ATM network components seamlessly is a major task for the near-term DISN ATM. The system architecture diagram for the DISN ATM network with ELAN services is shown by Figure 4.

Figure 4. ATM Architecture Diagram with ELAN Services.

The DISN ATM network is large in dimension, thus making the direct simulation computation almost impossible. To overcome such computational complexity, simulation and analysis are mixed for performance analysis routines. Quasi-simulation, approximation, and decomposition techniques are combined for the global network design and analysis. The developed models will compute queueing, processing delays, and appropriate propagation delays.

Let λ_{ij}^m be the aggregated offered traffic rate (packets or cells per second) for type m traffic demands originating from node i destined for node j . Let R_{ij} denote the number of alternate paths available from node i to node j and let $M_j(k)$ denote the number of hops for the k th path from i to j . Routing metric will assign the type- m traffic for path k a probability $P_{ij}^m(k)$. The traffic flow into the s th link of path k , is denoted by λ_s . D_s^m is the delay for type- m traffic at link s . Then the end-to-end expected delay from node i to node j for type- m traffic is

$$T_{ij}^m = \sum_{k=1}^{R_{ij}} P_{ij}^m(k) \sum_{s=1}^{M_j(k)} (D_s^m + \gamma_s) \quad (5)$$

where γ_s is the sum of node processing times, transmission delays, and propagation times. For a wide class of networks, it has been proven (see [5] and [8]) that the delay T_{ij}^m is convex and increasing in λ_{ij}^m . When simulation is used and the expected number of type m messages originating from node i and destined for node j is known as L_{ij}^m , then T_{ij}^m can also be obtained by using the Little's law (cf. [5]),

$$T_{ij}^m = L_{ij}^m / \lambda_{ij}^m \quad (6)$$

In ATM networks, the grade of service will be measured in terms of the cell loss probability. There are M different traffic types, type 1 being assigned the highest priority. Let $q_m(i,j)$ be the cell loss probability for type m traffic at link (i,j) . Then the cell loss probabilities will have the relation:

$$q_1(i,j) \leq q_2(i,j) \leq \dots \leq q_M(i,j) \quad (7)$$

Assuming the independence of cell loss probabilities at different links, the reliability of path (i,j) for type m traffic, r_{ij}^m , is next computed to be

$$r_{ij}^m = \sum_{k=1}^{R_{ij}} P_{ij}^m(k) \prod_{s=1}^{M_j(k)} (1 - q_m(s)) \quad (8)$$

The reliability of the network will be enhanced by rerouting and intelligent diagnostics to renetwork the system. Since ATM uses virtual connection management concerns, the management of virtual path and channels can be automated without being concerned with unnecessary network details. In case of a system failure, network restoration can be done expeditiously. The supporting DISN ATM network will provide sufficient redundancy and appropriate backup mechanisms will be provided for both hardware and software components.

V. SUMMARY

This paper has discussed ATM network services and designs for existing and planned DISN ATM networks. IP-over-ATM services are provided via ELANs and ATM virtual paths. Integrated network services of data, voice, and video are efficiently provided through the ATM network with high performance and guaranteed QoS. With large bandwidth capacities and fast processing times, virtual path services deliver better performance than conventional networks. Innovative ways of allocating and managing virtual paths in the ATM network were also presented. For the large-scale DISN ATM, simulation and analysis are mixed to produce requisite performance measures. Future architectural concepts such as MPOA are envisioned to further extend ELAN services.

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